

ISSN 2181-2357

XALQARO NAZARIY VA AMALIY TADQIQOTLAR
JURNALI

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL RESEARCH

JURNAL FARG'ONA POLITEXNIKA
INSTITUTI HAMKORLIGIDA NASHR
ETILADI

VOLUME 2,
Issue 4
2022

«Al-Ferganus» MChJ Nashriyot markazi.

A. M. Abdullayev

2-tom, 4-son.

«Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali»

Ilmiy jurnal.

April 2022 y.

2021 yil noyabrdan beri nashr etilmoqda.

Oyiga bir marta nashr etiladi. 16+

Tahririyat kengashi raisi Salomov O'ktam Raximovich, Rector of FerPI

Bosh muharrir K. I. Kurpayanidi

Tahririyat hay'ati: A.M.Abdullaev, M.S.Ashurov, E.A.Mo'minova, K.X.Abduraxmonov, A.N.Asaul, A.V.Burkov, U.V.G'ofurov, M.A.Ikromov, D.Kudbiev, E.S.Margianiti, B.Obrenovich, L.NA Sultonov, L.NA. , A.Xasanov, Sh.T.Karimov, Sh.Sh.Salixanova, U.K.Alimov, S.M.Turabdjano, B.A.Alimatov, R.J.Tozhiyev, A.A.Risqulov, B.M.Tursunov, A.A.Shermukhamedovsh, Y.S.A. H.A.Akramov, M.X.Hakimov, Sh.M.Iskandarova, Z.M.Sobirova, A.M.Muxtorova, L.M.Babaxo'jaeva.

Tahririyat manzili: 150107

Farg'ona shahri, Farg'ona ko'chasi, 86 -

uy

Тел. +998971003888

<https://alferganus.uz/en/site/index>

E-mail: alferganus.ltd@gmail.com

IF(Impact Factor) **8.7 / 2021**
<http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357>

TOGETHER WE REACH THE GOAL
SJIF 2022: 5,962
<http://sjifactor.com/passport.php?id=21994>

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti administratsiyasi huzuridagi axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligida ro'yxatga olingan.

Ro'yxatga olish № 1189 Berilgan sanasi: 17-06-2021.

Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali Crossref, OpenAIRE, Google Scholar bazalariga kiritilgan.

Impact-faktor 2021 Evaluation Pending

CC litsenziyasi turi: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0).

Jurnal jahon va mintaqaviy darajada fan va amaliyotning rivojlanish masalalariga bag'ishlangan.

Jurnal olimlar, o'qituvchilar, doktorantlar, talabalar uchun mo'ljallangan.

Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali.

2022. T. 2. №4. <https://alferganus.uz>

ISSN 2181-2357

9 772181 235007 >

© «Al-Ferganus» nashriyot markazi,
2022 Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

Publishing Center «Al-Ferganus» LLC.
A. M. Abdullaev
“International journal of theoretical and practical research”
Scientific Journal.
Published since November 2021.
Schedule: monthly. 16+

Volume 2, Issue 4
April, 2022.

Chairman of the Editorial Board Salomov Uktam Rakhimovich, FarPI rektori

Editor-in-chief K. I. Kurpayanidi

Editorial Board: A. M. Abdullaev, M. S. Ashurov, E. A. Muminova, K. Kh. Abdurakhmanov, A. N. Asaul, A. V. Burkov, U. V. Gafurov, M. A. Ikramov, D. Kudbiev, E. S. Margianiti, B. Obrenovich, L. Ivars, K. E. Onarkulov, N. A. Sultanov, A. Khasanov, Sh. T. Karimov, Sh. Sh. Khamdamova, D. S. Salikhanova, U.K. Alimov, S.M. Turabdzhanov, B.A.Alimatov, R.Zh. Tozhiev, A.A. Riskulov, B.M. Tursunov, A.A. Shermukhamedov, S. F. Ergashev, Y.S. Abbasov, Kh.A. Akramov, M.Kh. Khakimov, Sh.M. Iskandarova, Z.M. Sobirova, A.M. Mukhtarova, L.M. Babakhodzhaeva.

Address of the editorial office:

150107
Fergana city, Fergana str., 86.
Phone +998971003888

<https://alferganus.uz/en/site/index>

E-mail:
alferganus.ltd@gmail.com

IF(Impact Factor) **8.7 / 2021**
<http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357>

TOGETHER WE REACH THE GOAL
SJIF 2022: 5,962
<http://sjifactor.com/passport.php?id=21994>

Registered with the Agency of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
Registration No. 1189 dated 17-06-2021.

The journal "International Journal of Theoretical and Practical Research" is included Crossref, OpenAIRE, Google Scholar.

Impact-factor 2021 Evaluation Pending

License type supported CC: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0).

The Journal addresses issues of global and regional Science and Practice. For scientists, teachers, doctoral students, students.

(2022). International journal of theoretical and practical research, 2(4).

<https://alferganus.uz>

ISSN 2181-2357

9 772181 235007 >

© Publishing Center«Al-Ferganus»,
2022, Fergana, Uzbekistan

License type supported CC: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

Издательский центр «Al-Ferganus» ООО.

А. М. Абдуллаев

«Международный журнал теоретических и практических исследований»

Научный журнал.

Издается с ноября 2021 г.

Выходит один раз в месяц. 16+

Том 2, Номер 4.

Апрель 2022 г.

Председатель редакционного совета Саломов Уктам Рахимович, ректор ФерПИ

Главный редактор К. И. Курпаяниди

Редакционная коллегия: А.М.Абдуллаев, М.С.Ашуров, Э.А.Муминова, К.Х.Абдурахманов, А.Н.Асаул, А.В.Бурков, У.В.Гафуров, М.А.Икрамов, Д.Кудбиев, Э.С.Маргианити, Б.Обренович, Л.Иварс, К.Э.Онаркулов, Н.А.Султанов, А.Хасанов, Ш.Т.Каримов, Ш.Ш.Хамдамова, Д.С.Салиханова, У.К.Алимов, С.М.Турабджанов, Б.А.Алиматов, Р.Ж.Тожиев, А.А.Рискулов, Б.М.Турсунов, А.А.Шермухамедов, С.Ф.Эргашев, Ё.С.Аббасов, Х.А.Акрамов, М.Х.Хахимов, Ш.М.Искандарова, З.М.Собирова, А.М.Мухтарова, Л.М.Бабаходжаева.

Адрес редакции: 150107

г. Фергана, ул. Ферганская, 86

Тел. +998971003888

<https://alferganus.uz/en/site/index>

E-mail: alferganus.ltd@gmail.com

IF(Impact Factor) **8.7 / 2021**

[http://journalseeker.research](http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357)

[hbib.com/view/issn/2181-](http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357)

[2357](http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357)

TOGETHER WE REACH THE GOAL

SJIF 2022:5,962

[http://sjifactor.com/passp](http://sjifactor.com/passport.php?id=21994)

[ort.php?id=21994](http://sjifactor.com/passport.php?id=21994)

Зарегистрирован в Агентстве информации и массовых коммуникаций при Администрации

Президента Республики Узбекистан.

Регистрации № 1189 от 17-06-2021.

Журнал «Международный журнал теоретических и практических исследований» включен в Crossref, OpenAIRE, Google Scholar.

Импакт-факторы журнала: 2021 Evaluation Pending

Тип лицензии CC поддерживаемый журналом: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0).

В журнале рассматриваются вопросы развития мировой и региональной науки и практики. Для ученых, преподавателей, докторантов, студентов.

Международный журнал теоретических и практических исследований. 2022. Т. 2. №4.

<https://alferganus.uz>

ISSN 2181-2357

9 772181 235007 >

©Издательский центр «Al-Ferganus»,
2022, Фергана, Узбекистан

License type supported CC: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Iqtisodiy fanlar / Economic Sciences/ Экономические науки

1. **Faina Semyonovna Gafurova** 7
Process approach to the management of organization of labor at the enterprise as a factor of optimizing the labor activity of employees
2. **Gulnara Mukhamadzhonovna Davlyatova** 16
Socio-economic reforms in the views of the jadids and their role in the development of the economy
3. **Nodirahon Kurbanovna Juraeva** 35
improvement of management managements in the field of housing and utility services
4. **Murat Akramovich Ikramov, Maksat Muratovich Ikramov** 50
Issues of developing a marketing strategy for the development of the automotive industry of the republic of Uzbekistan
5. **Nilufar Muratovna Nabieva** 59
Some features of marketing research at service enterprises
6. **Paxlovon Yigitalievich Rakhmonazarov** 75
Increasing the effectiveness of management of ecological and economic systems in the region
7. **Odina Nabieva Tuychieva** 83
Modernization of production as a factor of increasing the efficiency of industrial enterprises
8. **Akramjon Ahmadjonovich Usmanov** 93
Application of economic methods of investment policies
9. **Dilnoza Khudoyberganova** 99
Importance of introduction of advanced technologies in the cultivation of fruit and vegetable products
10. **Barchinoy Yuldashevna Abdullayeva** 107
Improving the efficiency of innovation processes in the textile industry

Pedagogika fanlari / Pedagogical sciences/ Педагогические науки

11. **Murat Akramovich Ikramov** 116
Problems and solutions of training of intellectual personnel in the conditions of digitalization of the economy
12. **Zurab Panjikidze** 122
Academic mobility in the educational process
13. **Mukhaye Mirzasultanovna Tukhtasinova** 126
Issues of training a new generation of personnel in the conditions of the formation of the digital economy

Review of the monograph / monografiyaga taqriz / Рецензия на монографию

14. **Elnorakhon Abdukarimovna Muminova** 137
Review to the monograph of the Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor of the Department of Economics of the FerPI K. Kurpayanidi and PhD A.Ilyosov "Improving the organizational and economic

mechanisms of export of industrial products (on the example of the industrial sector of the Fergana region)"

E'lon / Reklama / Advertisement

<i>Advertisement</i>	140
<i>Our publications</i>	146

QR CODE of this issue of the magazine

Citation:

Panjikidze, Z. (2022). Academic mobility in the educational process. *SJ International journal of theoretical and practical research*, 2 (4), 122-125.

Panjikidze, Z. (2022). Academic mobility in the educational process. *SJ Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali*, 2 (4), 122-125.

Doi:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6656749>

Zurab, Panjikidze

PhD

Batumi Shota Rustaveli State
University, Batumi, Georgia

UDC 338.1

ACADEMIC MOBILITY IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

Abstract: *This article discusses the role of academic mobility in the educational sphere, namely, its causes. The advantages of this phenomenon and its consequences are revealed. The chronology of academic mobility, as well as statistics of students among different countries are studied.*

Keywords: *academic mobility, higher educational institution, quality of education, training program.*

Зураб Панджикидзе

PhD

Батумский государственный университет имени Шота Руставели,
г. Батуми, Грузия

**АКАДЕМИЧЕСКАЯ МОБИЛЬНОСТЬ В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ
ПРОЦЕССЕ**

Аннотация: *В статье рассмотрена роль академической мобильности в образовательной сфере, а именно, ее причины. Выявлены преимущества данного явления и ее последствия. Изучена хронология академической мобильности, а также статистика студентов среди различных стран.*

Ключевые слова: *академическая мобильность, высшее образовательное учреждение, качество образования, программа обучения.*

Introduction

The relevance of the research topic is due to a number of factors. The development of academic mobility of students in modern conditions acts as a strategic goal not only at the university level, but also nationwide. For a Georgian student, participation in mobility programs acts as a motivation for learning foreign languages, replenishing cultural and professional experience. It is important that after receiving this experience, students return back to their home university. On the one hand, it stimulates the process of international integration in higher education. On the other hand, it promotes the popularization of domestic values among students abroad.

Analysis and results

Under the influence of globalization, changes in the field of higher education in Georgia at the beginning of the XXI century acquire a systemic character, reflecting the direction and content of the process of internationalization of education as a whole. As a macro-educational parameter, internationality is now one of the key criteria for the quality of higher education in the country. The dynamics of the global scientific and educational space is characterized by a change in the positions of the leading subjects of science and higher education as a result of the development of the system of international academic mobility. In the process of exporting and importing educational services, the influence of different countries, including Georgia, on changes in the content and forms of organization of educational activities in the training of highly qualified specialists who are able to actively participate in the creation and use of the achievements of modern science for the benefit of all mankind is revealed.

The formation of conditions for the integration of education with science and industry, the creation of innovative infrastructure at the university and the region, the introduction of new standards in education, the development of forms of transnational education, the harmonization and unification of education systems and their integration into the global scientific and educational space require profound transformations in the field of higher education in Georgia. Consistent achievement of new strategic goals will contribute to the improvement of institutional mechanisms for the development of national education. The internationalization of higher education in Georgia at the turn of the XX–XXI centuries has created a solid foundation for the introduction of new principles for the formation and implementation of international academic mobility as a social process.

Global transformational changes in modern society have strengthened the main trends in the development of domestic universities:

- 1) development of mechanisms to enhance international academic mobility through the development of networking;
- 2) increasing the importance of intercultural communication in the scientific and educational space;
- 3) strengthening the differentiation of universities depending on the level of development and support of the region in which it is located;

4) the need to apply a network geographically differentiated approach in monitoring the effectiveness of domestic universities. These trends require rethinking the main models of higher school development and adjusting the priority directions in the strategy of Georgia's entry into the world scientific and educational space, which meets modern challenges.

The Bologna Process is a vivid example of an attempt by countries to unite in solving issues of international cooperation, recognition and equivalence of knowledge. Academic mobility of students in this context is one of the main goals of the Bologna Agreements. Moreover, in modern conditions, higher education institutions are in fierce competition with each other. Quantitative indicators of academic mobility (the number of foreign students, the number of participants in exchange programs or mobility programs, partnership agreements with foreign universities) not only allow the university to claim a worthy place in the world educational rankings, but also promote the image of the university on the world stage.

The term "academic mobility" is known to many students by various concepts (change of school, university, college or vocational training). And, especially, this topic is close to those students who have graduated from a university in another country and are studying today, as well as within one country. The relevance of academic mobility is primarily associated with an increase in scientific horizons or a change in the direction of training and obtaining new professional skills and abilities, as well as in-depth study according to the chosen training program.

Considering academic mobility in chronology, we can say that it was before. And the priority direction was European countries both then and today.

The important role of academic mobility is connected, first of all, in the in-depth study of the program in which the student studies, regardless of the level of education. Another important role of academic mobility is familiarization with new knowledge in a particular field of science. It can include new knowledge on the training program, which would not be taught in any other educational institution. The third role of academic mobility is the study of science from the point of view of the country in which the educational institution is located. And an equally important role of academic mobility is getting to know new people and familiarizing with the culture that exists in the country. This is an acquaintance with new people who may be friends in the future, as well as with new teachers who will open the doors to a completely new field of science for a student.

Despite such a number of advantages, academic mobility has negative sides.

Firstly, it is a possible outflow of "minds" from one country to another. The main reasons for this phenomenon are the advantages of studying science in another country (high achievement in science among countries) and high wages.

Secondly, it is the possibility of dissatisfaction in the chosen country or the chosen training program. However, this is unlikely, since students make choices based on what is closer to their specialization.

And thirdly, there is dissatisfaction in the culture of the chosen country. There are many examples of such a phenomenon, for example: I didn't like this country (although studying in this country was worth it); I didn't like the relationship in the country; it's unusual in a new foreign country.

If we consider the statistics of various countries that accept foreign students to study under various programs, and the countries from which those students leave, the statistics look like this. Top 6 countries that are popular with students: the United States of America, Great Britain, Germany, France, Australia and Canada. In addition to the leading countries, this list may include countries with a rapidly developing academic system in the future, which include: Japan, Spain, China, Italy, Austria, New Zealand, Switzerland, South Korea and the Netherlands. The top countries from which a large number of students leave are, first of all, China, India and South Korea (according to the report of the International Institute of Economics and Finance - ICEF - for 2021). According to UNESCO, these countries also include Germany, France, Saudi Arabia, the United States of America, Malaysia and Vietnam.

Conclusion

Thus, the role of academic mobility in the student's educational process is very important, because where and at what level the material on the discipline will be given, as well as what scientific basis the educational institution has, is of the utmost importance.

References:

1. Courtois, A., & Sautier, M. (2022). Academic Brexodus? Brexit and the dynamics of mobility and immobility among the precarious research workforce. *British Journal of Sociology of Education*.
2. Curaj, A., Deca, L., & Pricopie, R. (2018). *European higher education area: The impact of past and future policies* (p. 721). Springer Nature.
3. Gerhards, J., Hans, S., & Drewski, D. (2018). Global inequality in the academic system: effects of national and university symbolic capital on international academic mobility. *Higher Education*, 76(4), 669-685.
4. Knight, J., & De Wit, H. (2018). Internationalization of higher education: Past and future. *International Higher Education*, (95), 2-4.
5. Lee, J. T., & Kuzhabekova, A. (2018). Reverse flow in academic mobility from core to periphery: motivations of international faculty working in Kazakhstan. *Higher Education*, 76(2), 369-386.
6. Morley, L., Alexiadou, N., Garaz, S., González-Monteagudo, J., & Taba, M. (2018). Internationalisation and migrant academics: the hidden narratives of mobility. *Higher Education*, 76(3), 537-554.

ЭЪЛОН

Хурматли ҳамкасабалар “Al-Ferganus” нашриёти ва “Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali” электрон журнали Ўзбекистон таълим хизматлари бозорида ўзининг фаолиятини бошлаганлигини маълум қиламиз.

Ажойиб имкониятдан сиз биринчилар қаторида фойдаланиб илмий нашрларингизни чоп этишингиз мумкин.

“Al-Ferganus” нашриётимиз томонидан Сиз тақдим этган дарслик, ўқув қўлланма, монография ва илмий рисоаларга ISBN, Doi халқаро рақамли идентификаторларни бириктириш, уларнинг электрон замонавий андозадаги муқовалар ва ишланмаларнинг электрон макетини яратиш, нашриётда эълон қилинган ишларни электрон ахборот нашрларида жойлаштириш хизматлари кўрсатилади.

Бизнинг нашриётимизнинг бошқа нашриётлардан фарқи шундаки, тезкор ва сифатли хизмат кўрсатамиз ҳамда энг асосийси биз Сизнинг ишларингизни Алишер Навоий номидаги Ўзбекистон Миллий кутубхонаси ва Россия Миллий кутубхонаси фондларига бепул жойлашга шунингдек, Россия илмий иқтибослик индекси (РИНЦ ва E - library) платформасига, CrossRef базаларига шартнома асосида жойлаштиришга кўмаклашамиз.

“Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali” ISSN 2181-2357 электрон журнали ҳам ўз фаолиятини бошламоқда. Бизнинг журналда Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий аттестация комиссиясининг куйидаги ихтисосликлари физика-математика, кимё, биология, геология-минералогия, техника, қишлоқ хўжалиги,

тарих, иқтисодиёт, фалсафа, филология, география, юридик, педагогика, тиббиёт санъатшунослик, архитектура, психология, социология фанлари бўйича миллий ва хорижий муаллифларнинг фанлардан эришган ютуқлари ва истиқболлари борасидаги илмий мақолалари, илмий тадқиқотлар олиб бораётган олимларнинг илмий изланишлари натижалари эълон қилинади. Электрон журнал ҳар ойда бир марта эълон қилинади.

Журналларда эълон қилинадиган ҳар бир мақолага шартнома асосида DOI (Crossref) рақами берилади.

Шунингдек, таҳририят томонидан:

- мақолаларни сифатли таржима қилиш;
- мақолаларни таҳрирлаш ва журналлар талабига мослаш;
- мақолаларга ишлов бериш;
- мақолаларни плагиатга текшириш;
- хориждаги нуфузли (Scopus, Web of sciences ва юқори импакт факторли) журналларда мақолаларни сифатли ва ишончли чоп этишга кўмаклашиш хизматларини ҳам кўрсатади.

Имкониятни бой бериб қўйманг!

Қуйидаги манзилларга мурожаат қилинг:

Электрон почта манзили: Alferganus.ltd@gmail.com

Телеграмм манзилимиз : @Alferganus_ltd

Телефонлар: (97) 100-38-88

(91) 109-05-38

(97) 337-86-00

PUBLIC IDENTIFIERS OF INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL RESEARCH

PUBLISHER: AL-FERGANUS LLC - UZBEKISTAN

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ADDRESS^{IJA}

IJA.ZONE/16456457645 INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL RESEARCH^{IJA}

INTERNATIONAL ARTICLE ADDRESS^{IAA}

IJA.ZONE/1264564543 INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL RESEARCH^{IAA}

License type supported CC: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

ВНИМАНИЕ ОБЪЯВЛЕНИЕ!

Уважаемые коллеги! Сообщаем вам, что издательский дом «AL-FARGANUS» и «Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali» - «Международный журнал теоретических и прикладных исследований» начали свою деятельность на рынке образовательных услуг Узбекистана.

Это прекрасная возможность одним из первых опубликовать свои научные публикации. Наше издательство «AL-FARGANUS» предоставляет услуги по прикреплению международных цифровых идентификаторов ISBN, Doi к учебникам, учебным пособиям, монографиям и научным брошюрам, созданию электронных макетов их обложек и дизайнов в современной электронной форме, размещению опубликованных работ в электронные публикации.

Отличие нашего издательства от других издательств в том, что мы предоставляем быстрые и качественные услуги, а главное, бесплатно размещаем ваши работы в Национальной библиотеке Узбекистана им. Алишера Навои и оказываем помощь в размещении вашей работы в Российской национальной библиотеке, а также на платформе Российского индекса научного цитирования (РИНЦ, e-library) облегчить размещение.

Совместно с Ферганским политехническим институтом запущен проект электронного научного журнала «Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali - International Journal of Theoretical and Practical Research. Международный журнал теоретических и прикладных исследований».

Миссия научного электронного журнала направлена на развитие национальной и зарубежной науки, обеспечение общедоступности теоретических

позиций и практических результатов прикладных исследований. В журнале представлены следующие специальности Высшей аттестационной комиссии Республики Узбекистан по физике и математике, химии, биологии, геологии и минералогии, технике, сельскому хозяйству, истории, экономике, философии, филологии, географии, праву, педагогике, медицине, архитектуре, психологии, социологии. Журнал публикует научные статьи отечественных и зарубежных авторов о достижениях и перспективах науки, результатах научных исследований ученых, проводящих исследования. Электронный журнал издается один раз в месяц.

Каждой статье, опубликованной в журнале, на контрактной основе присваивается номер DOI (Crossref).

Также издательство оказывает услуги по:

- качественный перевод статей;
- редактирование статей и адаптация к требованиям журнала;
- обработка статей;
- проверка научных работ (статей, учебных пособий, монографий, диссертаций и др.) на плагиат статей;
- оказывает информационное обеспечение публикаций статей в престижных зарубежных журналах (Scopus, Web of Sciences и журналах с высоким импакт-фактором).

Не упускайте возможность!

Пожалуйста, свяжитесь с нами:

Электронный адрес: Alferganus.ltd@gmail.com

Наш адрес в телеграмм: @Alferganus_ltd

Телефоны: (97) 100-38-88

(91) 109-05-38

(97) 337-86-00

PUBLIC IDENTIFIERS OF INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL RESEARCH

PUBLISHER: AL-FERGANUS LLC - UZBEKISTAN

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ADDRESS^{IJA}

IJA.ZONE/16456457645

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL RESEARCH^{IJA}

INTERNATIONAL ARTICLE ADDRESS^{IAA}

IJA.ZONE/1264564543

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL RESEARCH^{IAA}

License type supported CC: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

2021-06-22 00:02:38

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi
huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy
kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi

№ 7430-3360-d0e2-4e5b-8cf1-9914-2923
Hujjat yaratilgan sana: 2021-06-22
Ariza raqami: 32087634

Hujjat berilgan: ОБЩЕСТВО С ОГРАНИЧЕННОЙ
ОТВЕТСТВЕННОСТЬЮ "AL-FERGANUS"
Qabul qiluvchining identifikatsiya raqami: 308291417

Ommaviy axborot vositasi davlat ro'yxatidan o'tkazilganligi to'g'risida
GUVOHNOMA

№ 1189

Nomi: "Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar"

Tarqatish shakli: jurnal

Til(lar)i: o'zbek, rus, ingliz

Muassis(lar)i: "AL-FERGANUS" mas'uliyati cheklangan jamiyat

Ixtisoslashuvi: fan sohalaridagi ilmiy nashr

Tahririyat manzili: 150100, Farg'ona viloyati, Farg'ona shahar, Mustaqillik ko'chasi, 42-uy

Tarqatish hududi: O'zbekiston Respublikasi hamda belgilangan tartibda chet davlatlarga

Berilgan sanasi: 17-06-2021

Ro'yxatdan o'tkazuvchi organ rahbari: Xodjayev Asadjon Azatbekovich

Mazkur hujjat Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2017 yil 15 sentyabrdagi 728-son qarori bilan tasdiqlangan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Yagona interaktiv davlat xizmatlari portali to'g'risidagi nizomga muvofiq shakllantirilgan elektron hujjatning nusxasi hisoblanadi. Elektron hujjatning nusxasida ko'rsatilgan ma'lumotlar to'g'riligini tekshirish uchun repo.gov.uz veb-saytiga o'ting va elektron hujjatning noyob raqamini kiriting yoki mobil telefon yordamida QR-kodni skaner qiling. Diqqat! Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2017 yil 15 sentyabrdagi 728-son qaroriga muvofiq elektron hujjatlardagi ma'lumotlar qonuniy hisoblanadi. Davlat organlariga Yagona portaldagi shakllantirilgan elektron hujjatlarning nusxalarini qabul qilishni rad etishlari qat'iy taqiqlangan.

9103

Our publications

Bizning nashrlarimiz

Наши издания

Курпаяниди К. И., Ил'осов А.А. Саноат маᖁсулотлари экспортининг ташкилий-иктисодий механизmlарини такомиллаштириш

(Фарғона вилояти саноат тармоғи мисолида): монография / Курпаяниди К. И., Ил'осов А.А.; М. А. Икрамов таҳрир остида. - Фарғона политехника институти. AL-FERGANUS, 2022. – 184 б.

ISBN 978-9943-7707-5-1

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6618980>

Kurpanyanidi K.I., Mamurov D.E. Management of innovative activity of business entities in industry: monograph / Kurpanyanidi K.I., Mamurov D.E.; edited by M.A.Ikramov. - Fergana polytechnic institute. AL-FERGANUS, 2022. – 200 p.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6475830>

Ashurov, M. S. Sanoat korxonalarida risklarni boshqarish mexanizmini takomillashtirish strategiyalari. Monografiya. Farg'ona: Al-Ferganus, 2022.- 120 b.

Ashurov Maxammadjon Sotvoldievich

Sanoat korxonalarida risklarni boshqarish mexanizmini takomillashtirish strategiyalari

Monografiya

Farg'ona - AL - FERGANUS - 2022

Abdullaev A.M., Kurpayanidi K. I., Khudaykulov A. S. Institutional transformation of the business sector. Monograph. Fergana "AL-FERGANUS", 2021. - 180 p.

A.M. Abdullaev, K.I. Kurpayanidi, A.Sh. Khudaykulov

INSTITUTIONAL TRANSFORMATION OF THE ENTREPRENEURIAL SECTOR

Monograph

Fergana - AL - FERGANUS - 2021

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5457089>

M.S. Ashurov, K.I. Kurpayanidi

RAQOBATBARDOSH MILLIY INNOVATSIYA TIZIMINI SHAKLLANTIRISH MUAMMOLARI VA YECHIMLARI

Monografiya

Farg'ona - AL - FERGANUS - 2021

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5676027>

ASHUROV M.S., SHAKIROVA Yu. S.

EKOLOGIK MUAMMOLAR VA ULARNI HAL QILISHDA EKOLOGIK MENEJMENTNING STRATEGIK YO'NALISHLARI

Monografiya

Farg'ona - AL - FERGANUS - 2021

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5722678>

Ashurov, M.S., Kurpayanidi, K.I. Problems and solutions for the formation of a competitive national innovation system. Monograph. Edited by Doctor of Economics, Professor Ikramov M.A., Fergana: Al-Ferganus, 2021.- 102 p.

Ashurov M.S., Shakirova Yu.S. Environmental problems and strategic directions of environmental management in their solution. Monograph. Edited by Doctor of Economics, Professor Ikramov M.A., Fergana: Al-Ferganus, 2021.- 160 p.

Жўраева, Н.Қ. Уй-жой коммунал соҳаси фаолиятини бошқариш механизмларини такомиллаштириш. Монография. - Фарғона: Al-Ferganus, 2021.- 140 б.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5335878>

Mirzaev, A.T. Methodological aspects of tourism and recreational activity management in Uzbekistan: changes and prospects: Monograph /Mirzaev A.T.; ed G. Sh. Khankeldiyeva - Fergana: Al-Ferganus, 2021.- 174 p.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5722700>

Э.А.Муминова

ЎҚИМАЧИЛИК САНОАТИ КОРХОНАЛАРИДА КОРПОРАТИВ БОШҚАРУВНИ ИННОВАЦИОН ПАРАДИГМАСИ: МЕТОДОЛОГИЯ, ТАЖРИБА ВА РИВОЖЛАНИШ ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ

Монография

Фарғона - AL - FERGANUS - 2021

Muminova, E.A. Innovative paradigm of corporate governance at textile enterprises: methodology, experience and development prospects: monograph /Muminova E.A.; ed. G. Sh. Khankeldiyeva - Fergana: Al-Ferganus, 2021.- 160 p.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5676091>

Н.М. Набиева

Хизмат кўрсатиш корхоналарини ривожлантиришнинг маркетинг стратегиясини ишлаб чиқиш

Монография

Фарғона - AL - FERGANUS - 2021

Набиева, Н.М. Хизмат кўрсатиш корхоналарини ривожлантиришнинг маркетинг стратегиясини ишлаб чиқиш. Монография. - Фарғона: Al-Ferganus, 2021.- 162 б.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5230368>

О.С.Назарматов

Nazarmatov, O.S. Improving the methodology of management of innovative processes in the enterprises of the textile industry. Monograph. - Fergana: Al-Ferganus, 2021.- 200 p.

ТУҚИМАЧИЛИК САНОАТИ КОРХОНАЛАРИДА
ИННОВАЦИОН ЖАРАЁНЛАРНИ БОШҚАРИШ
УСЛУБИЁТИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ

Монография

Фарғона - AL – FERGANUS - 2021

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5675967>

UBAYDULLAYEV M.M.

Ubaydullayev M.M. G'o'zada defoliatsiya o'tkazishning maqbul me'yor va muddatlari. Monografiya. /q.x.f.d., professor F.J. Teshayev muharrirligi ostida. Farg'ona: Al-Ferganus, 2021. – 160 b.

G'O'ZADA DEFOLIATSIYA O'TKAZISHNING
MAQBUL ME'YOR VA MUDDATLARI

Monografiya

Farg'ona - AL – FERGANUS - 2021

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5722721>

